

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Phosphorus effects on rice yield under different moisture regimes during wet season in West Bengal, India

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We conducted a field trial from 1986 to 1988 to study how P affected rice yield during wet season under different moisture regimes at a seed farm in Memari, Burdwan, in the Gangetic alluvial plains of West Bengal.

Soil is silt loam with pH 6.8, 0.9% organic C, CEC 15 meq/100 g soil, 73 kg available P/ha, and 21 6 kg exchangeable K/ha in the top 15 cm of soil.

The experiment was laid out in a random block design, replicated three times. P was applied as single

superphosphate (16% water soluble and 2% citric soluble P₂O₅) at 0, 30, 60, and 90 kg P/ha under three moisture regimes (see table). The crop received the recommended 80 kg N/ha and 41 kg K/ha and 48, 67, and 60 cm of rain during the growth periods in respective years. Irrigation was supplied as per treatment. IR36 raised in wetbed (60 kg seed/ha) was transplanted 30 d after seeding at 25 × 25-cm spacing with 2 plants/hill.

P up to 26 kg/ha significantly increased grain yield regardless of irrigation regime (see table). Grain yield was greater with continuous flooding at all P levels; however, grain yield/unit water input increased by 60% in the I₂ treatment compared with the continuous flooding. These results suggest that P fertilizer and irrigation water are substitutive inputs with regard to their interactive effects on yield. For example, total water input decreased by more than 40% from treatment I₀ to I₂ based on comparison of the pooled means. In

contrast, the I₀ treatment without P inputs and the I₂ treatment with 13 kg P/ha had equivalent grain yields of 4.5 t/ha.

Applying P can help stabilize yields on P-deficient soil when irrigation water is limited. □

Fertilizer management—organic

Intercropping green manure (GM) crops with dry season irrigated rice

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Legume crops can restore soil fertility that is depleted because of continuous cropping. But GM crops are rarely used in rainfed wetland rice-based cropping systems. *Sesbania aculeata* is sometimes intercropped with dry seeded or wet seeded rainfed lowland rice and *S. rostrata* can grow under flooded conditions. In trials during the 1991 dry season, we evaluated the effect of GM crops on dry season irrigated rice at varied planting dates and the subsequent use of this biomass for succeeding rice production.

Forty-day-old seedlings of BR14 were transplanted 29 Jan 1991 at 20 × 20-cm spacing. *S. aculeata* and *S. rostrata* were

Table 1. Yield of rice and GM sown on 4 dates (10, 20, 40, 60 DT) as affected by intercropping, 1991 dry season.

GM crop	Grain yield (t/ha)				GM biomass ^a (t/ha)			
	10	20	40	60	10	20	40	
<i>S. aculeata</i>	2.6	3.4	4.7	4.6	3.9	3.3	0.7	
<i>S. rostrata</i>	3.3	3.3	4.7	4.3	6.9	5.7	0.7	
Control	4.5	4.4	4.9	4.6	-	-	-	
SE	0.1				0.1			

^aAt 60 DT seed germination failed. GM crops were harvested on 25 May 1991.

P level effects on IR36 yield under 3 moisture regimes during rainy season in Indo-Gangetic Plains, West Bengal, India.

Year	Moisture regime ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)					Total water use ^b (cm)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)	
		0 kg P/ha	13 kg P/ha	26 kg P/ha	37 kg P/ha	Mean		0 kg P/ha	26 kg P/ha
1986	I ₀	4.1	4.6	5.0	5.1	4.7	88	46.6	56.8
	I ₁	4.0	4.5	4.8	4.8	4.5	55	72.7	87.3
	I ₂	3.9	4.4	4.7	4.9	4.5	45	86.7	104.4
	Mean	4.0	4.5	4.8	5.0				
1987	I ₀	4.7	5.2	5.5	5.7	5.3	99	47.5	55.6
	I ₁	4.3	4.6	5.0	5.1	4.7	67	64.2	74.6
	I ₂	4.0	4.4	4.7	4.7	4.4	52	76.9	90.4
	Mean	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.2				
1988	I ₀	4.8	5.3	5.7	5.7	5.3	90	53.3	63.3
	I ₁	4.5	4.9	5.2	5.3	5.0	65	69.2	80.0
	I ₂	4.3	4.7	5.2	5.2	4.9	58	74.1	89.7
	Mean	4.5	5.0	5.3	5.4				
Pooled	I ₀	4.5	5.0	5.4	5.5	5.1	92	48.9	58.7
	I ₁	4.2	4.7	5.0	5.1	4.7	62	67.7	80.6
	I ₂	4.0	4.5	4.9	4.9	4.6	52	76.9	94.2
	Mean	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.2				
LSD(0.05)	1986	1987	1988	Pooled					
P level	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1					
Moisture regime	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1					

^aI₀= continuous submergence of 5 ± 2 cm irrigation water, I₁= 5 ± 2 cm irrigation water 5 d after impounded water disappeared, and I₂= 5 ± 2 cm irrigation water 10 d after impounded water disappeared. Total water use = irrigation water applied (cm) plus rainfall (cm).

Table 2. Effect of incorporation of organic materials on some plant parameters, 1991 aus.^a

Treatment ^b	N rate (kg/ha)	Estimated N (kg/ha) from GM	Panicles (no./m ²)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total loss ^c for boro and aus (\$/ha)	Savings ^d from reduced N use (\$/ha)	Net loss (\$/ha)
P ₁ A	30	64	423 b	20.07 a	5.1 a	321.8	9.1	312.7
P ₁ R	30	119	461 a	19.42 bc	4.7 ab	289.5	9.1	280.4
P ₂ A	30	56	382 c	19.39 c	5.0 a	204.3	9.1	195.2
P ₂ R	30	102	432 b	19.38 c	4.8 a	240.0	9.1	230.9
P ₃ A	30	13	383 c	19.67 abc	4.3 b	173.7	9.1	164.6
P ₃ R	30	15	386 c	19.99 ab	4.7 ab	112.4	9.1	103.3
Control	60	-	389 c	19.45 bc	5.2 a			
CV (%)			3.60	1.71	5.9			

^aSmall letters compare means at P_{0.05} level by LSD. ^bP₁, P₂, and P₃ are the biomass of GM crops obtained from 10, 20, and 40 DT sowing. A = *S. aculeata*, R = *S. rostrata*. ^cRough rice @ \$0.17/kg. ^dUrea @ \$0.14/kg.

sown after every two rows of rice at 10, 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT). A split-plot design was used with three replications. Sowing time was in the main plots and GM crop in the subplots. Plots were 3 × 2 m. Irrigation water was drained out before sowing. GM crop seedlings at the 2- to 3-leaf stage were thinned to 50 plants/m².

Total biomass obtained from the GM crops was incorporated into the soil for the succeeding 1991 transplanted aus rice (wet season first crop) cultivation.

Twenty-nine-day-old seedlings of BR1 were transplanted 4 Jun 1991 at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Recommended fertilizer practices were followed in both seasons, except that N was cut by 50% when GM was used in aus.

Panicles/m², 1,000-grain weight, rice grain yield (adjusted to 14% moisture content), and GM biomass (after oven-dried at 70°C for 48 h) were recorded.

Rice grain yield was reduced by 22.3-41.3% at the first and second sowing of GM crops, perhaps because of shading from GM (Table 1). There was no significant yield reduction in the third sowing, but GM biomass production was less.

Panicles/m² and 1,000-grain weight differed significantly because of the added organic materials and reduced N in aus season (Table 2). Although GM seemed to contribute more N, aus rice plants do not use it for increased grain yield but rather for late tiller production. The initial slower decomposition of GM may have hampered growth of BR1, a short-duration variety. Heavier grains were obtained from plots with GM + 50% N. The net loss of \$103.00-313.00/ha due to intercropping in boro and reduced N use in aus rice indicates that the technology is unsuitable (Table 2).

We conclude that although N can be cut by 50% when 4-6 t GM/ha is incorporated, it is not a profitable system for improving soil fertility. □

Effect of continuous application of organic manure on the physical properties of soil in a rice - wheat cropping system

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Physical properties of soil after rice (1991) as influenced by continuous application of organic manures in a rice - wheat rotation. Punjab, India.^a

Properties	Fallow	FYM	Summer mung	Sesbania	LSD (0.05)
Infiltration rate (cm/h), 4 h after onset	0.35	0.40	0.55	1.00	0.16
Bulk density (g/cm ³)					
0-5 cm layer	1.48	1.45	1.37	1.36	0.08
5-10 cm layer	1.60	1.60	1.55	1.54	0.03
10-15 cm layer	1.65	1.62	1.59	1.57	0.06
15-20 cm layer	1.66	1.66	1.60	1.55	0.07
20-25 cm layer	1.62	1.64	1.59	1.59	ns
25-30 cm layer	1.56	1.54	1.56	1.52	ns
Water-stable aggregates (%)					
> 2 mm	13.39	21.75	13.73	15.45	4.94
1 - 2 mm	6.43	5.24	6.59	4.79	1.98
0.5 - 1 mm	7.96	6.96	5.61	7.75	2.89
0.25 - 0.5 mm	7.52	7.50	8.99	10.70	1.69
0.1 - 0.25 mm	6.27	7.05	7.79	11.13	2.40
Av grain yield ^a (t/ha)					
Rice	5.3	5.2	5.9	5.7	
Wheat	4.8	5.0	4.9	4.9	

^a Av of 6 yr.

Wet season rice followed by dry season (DS) wheat occupies most of the area under irrigation in Punjab. Soils of the region are generally lighter in texture and have high permeability. They are puddled before transplanting rice to maintain submerged conditions. Earlier studies indicated that puddling caused soil structure to deteriorate and to form a

dense layer below the puddled layer. This considerably reduced the yields of the following wheat crop.

We evaluated the physical properties of soil after the 1991 rice crop as influenced by continuous application of organic manure in a rice - wheat cropping system. We started this long-term experiment in 1984-85 DS.

Cumulative infiltration (after rice) as affected by continuous application of different organic manures.